

How to Enhance Word of Mouth in the Era of E-commerce: Case study of Tokopedia

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Abstract:

In this internet era, companies are racing to provide the best online shopping experience for their customers. Customer satisfaction is still one of the most crucial aspects in maintaining customer loyalty for their online shopping behavior. Tokopedia is one of the most advanced, growing, and well-known marketplaces for online shoppers in Indonesia. This paper will examine the word of mouth of online shoppers and also how to enhance it. It is also useful to be the basis for reference on the influence of perceived website quality, social influence and recommendation and experience on performance expectancy; performance expectancy for customer satisfaction and Word-of-Mouth; and customer satisfaction with Word-of-Mouth. This model was developed in order to conduct a Word-of-Mouth research conducted on the Tokopedia online shopping site in Surabaya. This research model is formed from the relationship between Perceived Website Quality, Social Influence and Recommendation, Experience, Performance Expectancy and Customer Satisfaction. This study used simple regression analysis to determine and test the hypothesis using SPSS software. Based on the data processing that has been done, the results show that Social Influence and Recommendation, and Experience have a significant effect on Performance Expectancy; Performance Expectancy has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction and Word of Mouth; Customer Satisfaction has a significant effect on Word of Mouth, while Perceived Website Quality has a positive but not significant effect on Performance Expectancy.

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Introduction

The Survey of the Association of Internet Service Providers in Indonesia mentioned that internet user penetration in Indonesia have reached 64.8% in 2018. The association is optimistic that the penetration of internet users will continue to increase as the development of network infrastructure development in various regions in Indonesia will continue to increase as well. The Secretary General of the Association, Henri Kasyfi, said that the results of the survey showed that the penetration of internet users in Indonesia in 2018 increased by 10.12% from the previous year. This increase have reached 27 million users. This means that there are 171.17 million internet users out of a total 246.16 million people of Indonesia based on Badan Pusat Statistik or Central Bureau of Statistics (<https://katadata.co.id/>, retrieved on 20 April 2020). The high level of internet access in Indonesia is a great opportunity to start a business in e-commerce. Daulay (2011) explains e-commerce as electronic commerce to carry out trade transactions using an internet network. The existence of e-commerce itself on the internet can be identified through the existence of the advertising, sales, and service support facilities for all customers by using a web-shaped online store that operates 24 hours a day. E-commerce business has many advantages, including expanding business partner networks, marketing reach, physically secure, effective, efficient, and flexible (Nugroho, 2016).

Tokopedia.com is one of five Indonesian unicorns. Tokopedia provides an opportunity for any stores, anyone, and any brands to join, open online stores, and manage their own stores. Tokopedia becomes a breakthrough site for entrepreneurs and producers who have financial constraints to open stores and expand market reach. Tokopedia allows transactions between sellers and buyers freely, without any territory restrictions. The site with the domain www.tokopedia.com has managed to become the first internet company in Southeast Asia that has won funding trust worth US \$ 100 million or around Rp 1.2 trillion from Softbank and Sequoia Capital. Softbank is the investor behind Alibaba's success, while Sequoia Capital is the investor behind the success of leading technology companies, such as Apple, Google, Instagram, WhatsApp, and others (<https://www.tokopedia.com/>, downloaded September 4, 2019). Tokopedia which is engaged in e-commerce needs to create a good perceived website quality in the eyes of the Indonesian people because the website is the main attraction and a main factor in the continuity of its business. Loureiro and Amorim (2017) state that perceived website quality is the user's evaluation of website features which can meet their needs and reflect the superiority of the website. To assess the quality of performance of an e-commerce website, the majority of people judge it first in terms of the external appearance that is on the website. The community thinks that the quality of the website reflects how the website will perform. So the better the quality of the Tokopedia website in the eyes of the public, the higher the performance expectancy that the public has of Tokopedia. According to Venkatesh et al. (2003), performance expectancy is the degree to which a person hopes that the use of a system will create benefits in terms of performance in his work. The level of expectation plays an important role as a comparison standard in evaluating the quality and satisfaction of a product. Expectations between one customer and another are always different, even for the same person, the expectations they have for a product will change over time. Another thing is also due to the influence of the customer's social environment.

Social influence is a change in an individual related to attitudes, beliefs and opinions that occur after interacting with other individuals or groups (Rachmawati, 2014). Whereas recommendations (Luwis and Harsini in Setyo and Utami, 2017) are a form of communication that gives rise to indirect promotions where those who provide these recommendations have

already bought a product or service before so that they share their experiences relating to it to others. Social influences and recommendations can both influence a person's purchasing decisions. Experience is interpreted as an episodic memory, a memory that receives and stores all events that have occurred in the past where this memory serves as a reference (Daehler and Bukatko, 1985 in Shah, 2003). Experience is one factor that can also influence a person's decision to use or purchase. Experience influences one's interest in doing online shopping, both the experience of shopping online in the past and experience in using technology. Satisfaction level according to Kotler (2002) is a feeling of pleasure or sadness someone who appears after comparing the real performance of a product with the expectations or expectations of the performance of the product. If consumers feel what they get is greater than their expectations, then they feel satisfied with the product and vice versa. In terms of marketing, the Word-of-Mouth (WOM) strategy is a strategy that is often used by companies because it is considered very effective in expediting the marketing process of a product or service. Kotler and Keller (2007) suggest that Word-of-Mouth (WOM) or more commonly known by word of mouth communication is giving recommendations both individually and in groups related to a product or service, which aims to provide personal information to opponents he spoke. In other words, WOM is a form of marketing activity where companies do not need to pay a large fee. At the end of the first semester of 2016, Tokopedia noted that 79.55% of visits came from mobile devices and the contribution of transactions from mobile had reached 73.58%. This percentage is far superior compared to last year in which visits from mobile devices reached 56% and transaction contributions were only around 29% (<http://lifestyle.liputan6.com/>, downloaded December 7, 2019). This shows that there is a positive WOM about Tokopedia that is circulating among the people so that within a period of just two years, the percentage of transaction contributions in Tokopedia has increased rapidly by 50%. The formulation of the problem in this study will be to test the significance of perceived website quality, social influence and recommendation, experience, performance expectancy, towards customer satisfaction and word of mouth. This study is useful to be the basis for reference on the influence of perceived website quality, social influence and recommendation and experience on performance expectancy; performance expectancy for customer satisfaction and Word-of-Mouth; and customer satisfaction with Word-of-Mouth. The results of this study can also be a reference for further research that has a similar topic.

Theoretical basis

Perceived Website Quality

Website quality is the quality of the technical dimensions, content, and appearance of a website that is considered important by the user so that it also influences the user's behavior and evaluation of the website (Al-Qeisi et al., 2014). According to Siagian and Cahyono (2014), website quality is a factor that can lead to customer trust and loyalty in conducting online buying and selling transactions through a site. Website quality is defined as an evaluation given by users regarding the functioning of website features in meeting their needs and is a reflection of the overall superiority of the website (Loureiro and Amorim, 2017).

Social Influence and Recommendation

Social influence is the result of interaction between one individual with another individual or group where changes occur in individuals related to attitudes, beliefs and opinions (Rachmawati, 2014). According to McGuire (in Rachmawati, 2014), social influence is an

influence that is felt by an individual where this influence is determined by the general nature and relative abilities that exist within the party giving the influence. Ghoni and Bodroastuti (2012) revealed that social influence is a condition where a consumer is influenced by social factors, such as reference groups, families, and roles and status. According to Wijaya (2014), a recommendation from another party is someone who receives a review given by another consumer which is able to influence the purchase decision of a product or service.

Experience is an internal and subjective customer response that arises as a result of direct and indirect interaction with the company (Meyer and Schwager, 2007). Experience is the interpretation of a consumer of his interactions with a brand (Frow and Payne, 2007). According to Robinnete and Brand (2008), experience is the experience that consumers feel about a product or service it uses. Gentile, Spiller, and Noci (2007) define experience as a set of interactions between consumers and products, companies, and parts of organizations where these interactions cause reactions that will determine how consumers act in the future. Rini (2009) suggests that experience is the involvement of the five senses, hearts, and minds of consumers, which can place the purchase of products or services in an important context in their lives. Experience is the embodiment of a brand that encompasses all interactions between companies and customers (Watkins, 2007).

Performance expectancy is the degree to which a person hopes that the use of a system will create benefits in terms of performance in his work (Ghalandari et al., 2012). Jati (2012) revealed that performance expectancy is someone who believes that the use of a system or technology will be very useful and can improve the performance and work performance it does. Performance expectancy is an individual's belief that his performance will improve if he uses technology (Agustina, 2013). In the context of mobile wallet, mobile payment, and mobile banking, performance expectancy is defined as the user's desire to make transactions more efficiently, comfortably, and quickly (Bhimasta, 2017).

Customer satisfaction is a reaction that arises in a person, which is the result of a difference or gap between expectations before purchase with the results felt after purchase (Wardhana, 2016). According to Schiffman and Kanuk (2010), customer satisfaction is an individual consumer's perception of the performance of the product or service used so far which is whether the product or service has met its expectations or not. According to Salim et al. (2015), customer satisfaction is the initial factor affecting consumer intentions in making repeat purchases to be high.

Word-of-Mouth. According to Ghalandari et al. (2012), Word-of-Mouth is behavior that arises in a person after making a purchase of a product or service. According to Parsa and Sadeghi (2015), Word-of-Mouth is a level where customers can influence friends, relatives, and people around them to become aware of a product where this will create a certain level of satisfaction. Hart et al. (in Parsa and Sadeghi, 2015) states that consumers with a bad experience of a product or service, will talk about it to 11 individuals while consumers with a pleasant experience, will only talk about it to 6 individuals. According to the theory of asymmetric effects of positive and negative events, this happens because negative experiences lead to stronger responses in a person than responses generated by positive experiences.

The Effect of Perceived Website Quality on Performance Expectancy

Kim and Lee (2014) state that the quality of a system influences the level of community acceptance and adoption of an information system, through perceived usefulness and user satisfaction. When the quality of an information system or site is considered good, users will perceive that the system or site is more useful so that they believe that it will be able to increase their productivity (creating efficiency). Users who feel confident in the quality of a website that they use, will increase their perception regarding the usefulness and performance of the website (Loureiro and Amorim, 2017). So it can be concluded that the more someone perceives the quality of a good website, the higher the performance expectancy that is created related to the website. Therefore, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H1: Perceived website quality has a significant effect on performance expectancy.

The Influence of Social Influence and Recommendation on Performance Expectancy

Loureiro and de Araujo (2014) state that someone who is motivated by those around him to use an e-commerce site and make a purchase from there, will tend to have the perception that the technology is very useful so as to lead to high performance expectancy. Based on research conducted by Sung et al. (2015), social influence has a positive influence on performance expectancy. The social influence obtained by someone from the surrounding environment will affect how they expect. As more and more people around him give recommendations and influence to him to use a system, the more he has the perception that the system does have good quality and performance as well as satisfying. Until finally when he accepts these recommendations, he will have high performance expectations. Therefore, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H2: Social influence and recommendation has a significant effect on performance expectancy.

Effect of Experience on Performance Expectancy

According to Agarwal and Prasad (1999) and Jiang et al. (2000), one's internet experience influences both perceived usefulness and ease of use, which in turn affects one's interest in using a system. The high level of knowledge and the wealth of experience around the internet will make it easier for someone to use and adopt a new system. This is because they are used to using technology so that when there is a new technology system, they will not be surprised but instead tend to easily adjust it. In other words, the more a person has extensive technological knowledge and also has experience, the higher the standard of performance he has regarding a system. Therefore, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H3: Experience has a significant effect on performance expectancy.

The Effect of Performance Expectancy on Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction occurs when the needs or expectations (expectations) of performance owned by consumers can be met through interaction with the company (Tjiptono, 2011). Often what becomes the performance expectations of a system, comes from the performance needs of the person himself. When the expectations of performance can be met, then someone will feel satisfied with the use of the system. Therefore, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H4: Performance expectancy has a significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Effect of Performance Expectancy on Word-of-Mouth

Loureiro and Amorim (2017) state that the fulfillment of one's desires on the performance of a service or technology will make it easier for that person to communicate the positive experience he feels to others. In other words, communicating this positive experience can occur because the performance expectancy possessed has been fulfilled. In this case, communicating a positive experience will lead to a recommendation for others to join using the same site. Therefore, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H5: Performance expectancy has a significant effect on Word-of-Mouth

Effect of Customer Satisfaction on Word-of-Mouth

Satisfied customers will be willing to recommend the services they get from a product or service to those around them (Palmatier et al., 2006; Morgan and Rego, 2006). In other words, positive Word-of-Mouth can be created if the customer is satisfied with a product or service that has been used so far. Barata (2007) states that if consumers are satisfied with a product or service it uses, then the consumer will give a reference to their friends or acquaintances to use similar products or services. So it can be concluded that in order to create positive Word-of-Mouth, companies need to ensure that consumers are satisfied with the use of the products or services they create. Therefore, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H6: Customer satisfaction has a significant effect on Word-of-Mouth.

Research Model

Research methodology

Research conducted using quantitative research methods which type is included in the type of causal associative research. The purpose of this study is to develop a previous research model and apply it to this study, which aims to test the research hypotheses that have been previously stated in the literature review and answer existing problems. Umar (2003) states that asositif research is research that aims to examine the influence between variables. Whereas Sugiyono (2007) states that causal research is carried out to analyze the causal relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Therefore, it can be concluded that causal associative research is used in this study because this study examines the influence between variables where the effect arising from one variable to another variable will create a causal relationship (causal). In this study, data collection was

done by distributing questionnaires. Questionnaires were distributed in writing to Tokopedia site customers in Surabaya. After the respondent completes the questionnaire, only data from the questionnaire that actually meets the sample characteristic criteria, will be taken for further processing. To answer each statement in the questionnaire, a Likert scale will be used from a scale of 1 to 5 in which each scale represents the answer of strongly disagree to strongly agree. Before data processing is carried out, the validity and reliability tests will be conducted first. Validity is the accuracy or accuracy of an instrument in measuring something you want to measure. Validity test is often used to measure the accuracy of an item in a questionnaire or the scale associated whether the items on the questionnaire are appropriately used to measure what you want to measure. The testing technique used in testing validity is Bivariate Pearson Product Moment Correlation. According to Wijaya (2009), if $r_{\text{statistics}} > r_{\text{table}}$, the instrument can be declared valid. The reliability test is a study related to the degree of consistency between various measurements of a variable. Cronbach's Alpha is the method most often used to measure the reliability value of data that has been collected. According to Wijaya (2009), if the alpha coefficient > 0.6 then the instrument can be declared reliable. Regression analysis is a statistical technique used to analyze the effect of one or more independent variables on one dependent variable. The purpose of multiple regression analysis is to use the value of known independent variables to predict the value of the dependent variable. According to Hair et al. (2006), each independent variable is weighted by a regression analysis procedure to ensure maximum predictions from a set of independent variables. Referring to the research model used, based on the regression analysis the following equation will be as follows:

$$PE = b_1.PWQ + b_2.SIR + b_3.E$$

$$S = b_4.PE$$

$$WOM = b_4.PE + b_5.S$$

Data analysis

Of the 200 questionnaires distributed there were 125 questionnaires that returned according to the characteristics and could be processed. Respondents in this study are Tokopedia site users aged 17-55 years, domiciled in Surabaya, have made online purchases through the Tokopedia site in the past six months, have accessed online reviews through the Tokopedia site in the past six months, and have done a Word-of-Mouth about the Tokopedia site to people around. In this study the whole validity test was done with the number of samples (n) = 125 and $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) so that $r_{\text{table}} = 0.176$ was obtained. Based on testing it is known that the calculated value of all indicators is greater than the table. Therefore, it can be concluded that all indicator variables in this study are valid. Based on testing on the reliability test results table, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha value of all indicators is greater than 0.6. Therefore, it can be concluded that all indicator variables in this study are reliable.

Table 1. Multiple Perceived Website Quality (PWQ) Regression, Social Influence and Recommendation (SIR), and Experience (E) on Performance Expectancy (PE)

Model / Variable	R	Adj R ²	F _{sig}	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t _{sig}	Hypothesis
PWQ,SIR,E*PE	0,674	0,441	0,000			
PWQ				0,188	0,107	Not Supported
SIR				0,264	0,001	Supported
E				0,353	0,006	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Based on Analysis of Multiple Regression Perceived Website Quality (PWQ), Social Influence and Recommendation (SIR), and Experience (E) on Performance Expectancy (PE), the R value is 0.674. This explains that there is a strong correlation. The adjusted R² value of 0.441 indicates Perceived Website Quality, Social Influence and Recommendation, and Experience is able to explain 44.1% Performance Expectancy, while the remaining 55.9% is influenced by other variables not included in this research model. F test results show a significance value of 0,000, this means the research model is acceptable. Based on table 1 can be produced the following regression equation:

$$PE = 0.188 PWQ + 0.264 SIR + 0.353E$$

The positive coefficient indicates the direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable. While the coefficient that is negative indicates the change is not in the direction of the independent variable with the dependent variable. From the results of t tests that have been carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. Perceived Website Quality (PWQ) has a significant effect on Performance Expectancy (PE) rejected at the level of sig. .107 > sig. 0.05.
2. Social Influence and Recommendation (SIR) significantly influence the Performance Expectancy (PE) received at sig. 0.001 < sig. 0.05.
3. Experience (E) has a significant effect on Performance Expectancy (PE) received at the level of sig. 0.006 < sig. 0.05.

Table 2. Simple Regression of Performance Expectancy (PE) on Customer Satisfaction (CS)

Model / Variable	R	Adj R ²	F _{sig}	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t _{sig}	Hypothesis
PE*CS	0,590	0,348	0,000			
PE				0,590	0,000	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Based on Simple Regression Analysis Performance Expectancy (PE) to Customer Satisfaction (CS) obtained an R value of 0.590. This explains that there is a strong correlation. The adjusted R² value of 0.348 indicates Performance Expectancy is able to explain 34.8% of Customer Satisfaction, while the remaining 65.2% is influenced by other variables not included in this research model. F test results show a significance value of 0,000, this means the research model is acceptable. Based on table 2 we can produce the following regression equation:

$$CS = 0,590PE$$

The positive coefficient indicates the direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable. While the coefficient that is negative indicates the change is not in the direction of the independent variable with the dependent variable. From the results of t tests that have been carried out, it can be concluded that: **1. Performance Expectancy (PE) has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction (CS) received at the level of sig. 0,000 < sig. 0.05.**

Table 3. Performance Expectancy (PE) and Customer Satisfaction (CS) Multiple Regression of Word of Mouth (WOM)

Model / Variabel	R	Adj R ²	F _{sig}	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t _{sig}	Hypothesis
PE,CS*WOM	0,727	0,521	0,000			
PE				0,342	0,000	Supported
CS				0,471	0,000	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Based on Multiple Regression Analysis of Performance Expectancy (PE) and Customer Satisfaction (CS) against Word of Mouth (WOM), the R value is 0.727. This explains that there is a strong correlation. The adjusted R² value of 0.521 shows that Performance Expectancy and Customer Satisfaction are able to explain 52.1% of Word of Mouth, while the remaining 47.9% is influenced by other variables not included in this research model. F test results show a significance value of 0,000, this means the research model is acceptable. Based on table 3 we can produce the following regression equation:

$$\text{WOM} = 0,342\text{PE} + 0,471\text{CS}$$

The positive coefficient indicates the direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable. While the negative coefficient indicates the change is not in the direction of the independent variable with the dependent variable. From the results of t tests that have been carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. Performance Expectancy (PE) has a significant effect on Word of Mouth (WOM) received at the sig. 0,000 < sig. 0.05.
2. Customer Satisfaction (CS) has a significant effect on Word of Mouth (WOM) received at the level of sig. 0.251 > sig. 0.05.

Discussion

Based on the results of multiple regression analysis, the results obtained that the first hypothesis which reads Perceived Website Quality has a positive effect, although not significantly to Performance Expectancy. This is consistent with the results of research conducted by van Iwaarden et al. (2004) and Kim and Lee (2014) which state that the visual appeal and content of a website affect an individual's perception of the usefulness, enjoyment, and ease of use of the site where the visual and content are seen as a reflection of quality. Loureiro and Amorim (2017) state that users who feel confident in the quality of a website that they use, will increase their perceptions regarding the usefulness and performance of the website. Social Influence and Recommendation and Experiences have a positive and significant influence on Performance Expectancy. Research conducted by Venkatesh et al. (2003) and Loureiro and de Araujo (2014) which states that someone who is motivated by those around him to use an e-commerce site and make a purchase from there, will tend to have the perception that the technology is very useful so as to cause high performance expectancy. Lin et al. (in Shen et al., 2006) states that an individual tends to accept references and recommendations from other people for consideration when that person feels that the technology is indeed useful. In other words, someone who accepts recommendations from others to use a system, has high expectations that the performance of the system will be able to meet their needs and desires. Davis et al. (1992) revealed that the experiences that an individual has experienced also influence the perceived usefulness (performance expectancy) possessed by that person. Agarwal and Prasad (1999) and Jiang et al. (2000) also stated that the internet experience a person has, affects both the perceived usefulness and ease of use (performance expectancy) of the person where this ultimately affects their interest in using a system. Performance Expectancy has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. Research conducted by Anderson (1973) and Oliver (1993) revealed that customer satisfaction is the result of differences in perceived performance with those expected by someone. Tjiptono (2011) states that customer satisfaction occurs when the needs or expectations (expectations) of performance owned by consumers can be met through their interactions with the company. The level of satisfaction felt by an individual will be higher if the difference between the perceived performance and the expected, the smaller. In other words, the more performance expectancy a user of a site has, the more satisfied he will be. Performance

Expectancy (PE) has a significant effect on Word-of-Mouth (WOM). Loureiro and Amorim (2017) state that the fulfillment of one's desires for the performance of a service or technology will make it easier for that person to communicate the positive experience he feels to others. In this case, communicating a positive experience will lead to a recommendation for others to join using the same site. O'Loughlin and Coenders (2002) states that consumer loyalty is measured and demonstrated by the intention to repurchase, price tolerance, and willingness to recommend products or services to others. Furthermore, Goodman (2009) states that when a product has a good performance, consumers will share the experience with two people while when a product has a poor performance, consumers will share the experience with six people. So it can be concluded that in this case, the good performance of a product in meeting the expectations of its users, will be able to make them do positive Word-of-Mouth to those around them. Customer Satisfaction (CS) has a significant influence on Word-of-Mouth (WOM) according to the results of research conducted by Palmatier et al. (2006) and Morgan and Rego (2006) which state that satisfied customers will be willing to recommend the services they get from a product or service to those around them. Buttle (1998) states that satisfaction and excitement that arises in a consumer related to the use of a product or service, will motivate the person to do positive Word-of-Mouth. In other word, satisfaction is a feeling of "excessive" joy that arises from the use of a product, which tends to make the person excited to express his joy to those around him.

Conclusion

This model was developed in order to conduct a Word-of-Mouth research conducted on the Tokopedia online shopping site in Surabaya. This research model is formed from the relationship between Perceived Website Quality, Social Influence and Recommendation, Experience, Performance Expectancy and Customer Satisfaction. Based on the data processing that has been done, the results show that Social Influence and Recommendation, and Experience have a significant effect on Performance Expectancy; Performance Expectancy has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction and Word of Mouth; Customer Satisfaction has a significant effect on Word of Mouth, while Perceived Website Quality has a positive but not significant effect on Performance Expectancy.

Recommendation

Seeing the results of existing research where there are still many limitations on the research conducted by the author, further research is expected to be able to complete the variables that already exist in this study so that can further enhance understanding of the factors that influence Word-of-Mouth. Further research can broaden the scope of respondents to be studied or conduct research in areas that are different from the research that has been done at this time. The goal is that further research carried out can increasingly provide a broad picture of Word-of-Mouth. dilakukan dapat semakin memberikan gambaran luas terhadap *Word-of-Mouth*.

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